

Exploiting symmetries in active set enumeration for constrained linear-quadratic optimal control [★]

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Abstract

This paper studies symmetric constrained linear-quadratic optimal control problems. The parametric solution to these problems is a piecewise-affine feedback law that can be equivalently expressed as a set of active sets. We show symmetries of the optimal control problem entail symmetries of the active sets, which can be used to simplify finding the set of active sets considerably. Specifically, we improve a recently proposed method for the dynamic-programming-based enumeration of all active sets. The achieved reduction of the computational effort is illustrated with examples.

Key words: constrained LQR, model predictive control, combinatorial quadratic programming

1 Introduction

The parametric solution to a constrained linear-quadratic optimal control problem (OCP), which is required for explicit linear model predictive control, for example, is a piecewise-affine feedback law [4,19]. Every affine piece can be assigned a unique active set, so the solution can be equivalently expressed by a set of active sets. The calculation of the solution often is computationally demanding particularly for high-order problems and problems with long horizons. An entire field of research focuses on the reduction of the computational effort, various approaches exist.

Geometric approaches exploit relations of neighbored affine pieces in the solution [4,20,2]. These approaches are competitive and established in mature software toolboxes [12,3]. Combinatorial approaches, also referred to as implicit enumeration techniques, calculate the set of

active sets that defines the solution by taking advantage of relations of active sets [10,9,17,1,11]. Recently, the combinatorial approach was combined with dynamic programming (DP) techniques [15,16].

The present paper studies symmetric constrained linear-quadratic OCPs. The symmetries of the OCP are reflected in input- and space transformations in the associated piecewise-affine feedback law [7]. This is used to reduce the memory requirements of the solution [5,8]. For the special case of problems with constraints that are point-symmetric to the origin, there exist pairwise symmetric active sets with similar properties [9,14]. It is an obvious question how general symmetries are reflected in the active sets.

We show that a symmetry of a constrained linear-quadratic OCP results in a symmetry in the set of the active set. Consequently, the set of all active sets can be represented by a subset thereof and the symmetric counterparts of the elements of this subset. This insight can be exploited to both reduce the effort required to construct all active sets and the memory necessary to store all active sets. We propose an exploration strategy for the combinatorial tree such that the symmetric active sets are not considered. The reduction achieved by these improvements is analyzed by applying this strategy to the DP approach from [15].

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Section 2 introduces constrained linear-quadratic OCPs, their symmetries, and the DP approach. Section 3 identifies symmetries in active sets, states properties of symmetric active sets, and proposes an exploration strategy for the combinatorial tree. The improved DP approach is presented in Sect. 4. Section 5 applies this approach to examples. Conclusions are given in Sect. 6.

1.1 Notation

Consider a matrix $M \in \mathbb{R}^{a \times b}$ and an ordered set $\mathcal{M} \subseteq \{1, \dots, a\}$. Let $M_{\mathcal{M}} \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{M}| \times b}$ denote the submatrix of M containing all rows indicated by \mathcal{M} . We say the sets \mathcal{M}_1 and \mathcal{M}_2 partition the set \mathcal{M} if $\mathcal{M}_1 \cup \mathcal{M}_2 = \mathcal{M}$ and $\mathcal{M}_1 \cap \mathcal{M}_2 = \emptyset$. Furthermore, let $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{M})$ refer to the power set of a set \mathcal{M} and let $\min(\mathcal{M})$ and $\max(\mathcal{M})$ denote the smallest and greatest element of \mathcal{M} , where applicable. Let the operators \oplus , \otimes and \circ denote the Minkowski addition, Kronecker product, and Hadamard product, respectively. Finally, let $I^a \in \mathbb{R}^{a \times a}$ and $0^{a \times b} \in \mathbb{R}^{a \times b}$ denote the identity and zero matrices, respectively.

2 Problem statement and preliminaries

We consider the classical constrained linear-quadratic OCP

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{U, X} \quad & \|x(N)\|_P^2 + \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \left(\|x(k)\|_Q^2 + \|u(k)\|_R^2 \right) \quad (1a) \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & x(k+1) = Ax(k) + Bu(k), \quad k = 0, \dots, N-1 \quad (1b) \\ & u(k) \in \mathcal{U}, \quad k = 0, \dots, N-1 \quad (1c) \\ & x(k) \in \mathcal{X}, \quad k = 0, \dots, N-1 \quad (1d) \\ & x(N) \in \mathcal{T}, \quad (1e) \end{aligned}$$

where $N \in \mathbb{N}$ is the horizon, inputs $u(k) \in \mathbb{R}^m$ and states $x(k) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ are collected in $U = (u^T(0), \dots, u^T(N-1))^T \in \mathbb{R}^{Nm}$ and $X = (x^T(1), \dots, x^T(N))^T \in \mathbb{R}^{Nn}$, respectively, $x(0)$ is given, $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ and $B \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$ define the discrete-time time-invariant linear system, the pair (A, B) is stabilizable, $\mathcal{U} \subset \mathbb{R}^m$ and $\mathcal{X} \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ are compact full-dimensional polytopes that contain the origin in their interiors, $R \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$, $R \succ 0$ and $Q \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $Q \succeq 0$ are the weighting matrices for inputs and states, respectively, the pair $(Q^{\frac{1}{2}}, A)$ is detectable, $P \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is the optimal cost function matrix of the unconstrained infinite-horizon problem which implies $P \succ 0$, and $\mathcal{T} \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ is the largest possible set such that the optimal feedback for the unconstrained infinite-horizon problem stabilizes the system without violating the constraints. Let the total number of halfspaces in (1) and, equivalently, inequalities in (2) below be denoted q . Furthermore, let \mathcal{Q} denote the index set $\{1, \dots, q\}$.

By substituting (1b), (1) can be transformed into a quadratic program (QP) of the form

$$\begin{aligned} \min_U \quad & \frac{1}{2}x(0)^T Y x(0) + x(0)^T F U + \frac{1}{2}U^T H U \quad (2) \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & G U \leq E x(0) + w, \end{aligned}$$

with $Y \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $F \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times Nm}$, $H \in \mathbb{R}^{Nm \times Nm}$, $G \in \mathbb{R}^{q \times Nm}$, $E \in \mathbb{R}^{q \times n}$, and $w \in \mathbb{R}^q$. The assumptions on (1) imply $H \succ 0$ [4].

For any $x(0)$ such that (2) has a solution, let $U^*(x(0))$ denote the optimal solution to (2). Furthermore, let $\mathcal{A}(x(0))$ and $\mathcal{I}(x(0))$ refer to the optimal active set and inactive set, respectively, where

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}(x(0)) &:= \{i \in \mathcal{Q} \mid G_{\{i\}} U^*(x(0)) = w_{\{i\}} + E_{\{i\}} x(0)\}, \\ \mathcal{I}(x(0)) &:= \mathcal{Q} \setminus \mathcal{A}(x(0)). \end{aligned}$$

We often drop $x(0)$. We call an active set \mathcal{A} *optimal* if it is optimal for some $x(0)$.

Solving (2) as a parametric program with parameter $x(0)$ results in an optimal control law $x(0) \mapsto U^*(x(0))$ that is a continuous piecewise affine function of $x(0)$ on a polytopic partition [4, Sect. 4.1]. Let the set \mathcal{M}_N collect all optimal active sets \mathcal{A} such that \mathcal{A} defines a full-dimensional polytope in state-space and such that $G_{\mathcal{A}}$ has full row rank. Let the set \mathcal{S}_N collect all optimal active sets \mathcal{A} including those such that \mathcal{A} defines a lower-dimensional polytope (facet, vertex, etc.) and those such that $G_{\mathcal{A}}$ does not have full row rank ($\mathcal{S}_N \supseteq \mathcal{M}_N$).

2.1 Group theory and symmetries of OCPs

We introduce some basic facts of group theory as a preparation. Details can be found in standard texts, e.g., in [13].

A set together with an operator is a group if the operator is associative, the set is closed under the operator, the set includes the identity element, and the set includes the inverse of each of its elements. A permutation that acts on the set \mathcal{M} is a bijective function that maps \mathcal{M} to itself. A permutation group is a set of permutations that satisfies the axioms group stated above. The operator is function composition.

Let a permutation group act on the set \mathcal{M} . The orbit $\mathcal{O}(a)$ for an $a \in \mathcal{M}$ contains the images of a under all permutations that are element of the permutation group. The orbits $\mathcal{O}(a)$ of all $a \in \mathcal{M}$ partition \mathcal{M} .

Following [8, Def. 4] we call an OCP (1) symmetric to the pair of invertible matrices (Θ, Ω) , with $\Theta \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$

and $\Omega \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$, if the pair (Θ, Ω) satisfies

$$\Theta A = A\Theta, \quad \Theta B = B\Omega, \quad (3a)$$

$$\Theta \circ \mathcal{X} = \mathcal{X}, \quad \Omega \circ \mathcal{U} = \mathcal{U}, \quad \Theta \circ \mathcal{T} = \mathcal{T}, \quad (3b)$$

$$\Theta^T Q \Theta = Q, \quad \Omega^T R \Omega = R, \quad \Theta^T P \Theta = P, \quad (3c)$$

which are the symmetry of the dynamics, constraints, and cost, respectively.

Let the set \mathcal{G} contain all (Θ, Ω) that satisfy (3) for an arbitrary but fixed OCP (1). The set \mathcal{G} is a group under pairwise matrix multiplication. The relations

$$(I^m, I^m) \in \mathcal{G}, \quad (4a)$$

$$(\Theta, \Omega) \in \mathcal{G} \Rightarrow (\Theta^{-1}, \Omega^{-1}) \in \mathcal{G}, \quad (4b)$$

$$(\Theta_1, \Omega_1), (\Theta_2, \Omega_2) \in \mathcal{G} \Rightarrow (\Theta_1 \Theta_2, \Omega_1 \Omega_2) \in \mathcal{G} \quad (4c)$$

hold [8, Thm. 2 and Proof of Prop. 1].

2.2 Dynamic programming approach

We summarize the DP approach presented in [15] as needed for comparison in Sect. 5.1. Furthermore, this approach is improved for problems with symmetries in Sect. 4.

The approach solves constrained linear-quadratic OCPs by iteratively increasing the horizon from the initial horizon $N = 1$ to some target horizon $N = N_{\max}$. It requires the constraints in (1) and (2) to be ordered by increasing stage

$$\begin{aligned} u(0) \in \mathcal{U}, \quad x(0) \in \mathcal{X}, \\ \vdots \\ u(N-1) \in \mathcal{U}, \quad x(N-1) \in \mathcal{X}, \\ x(N) \in \mathcal{T} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

with stages $k = 0, \dots, N$. Let $q_{\mathcal{U}\mathcal{X}}$ and $q_{\mathcal{T}}$ denote the number of halfspaces that define \mathcal{U} and \mathcal{X} , and \mathcal{T} , respectively. Let the set $\mathcal{Q}_0 = \{1, \dots, q_{\mathcal{U}\mathcal{X}}\}$ contain the indices of all constraints on $x(0)$ and $u(0)$.

The solution for the initial horizon \mathcal{S}_1 can be constructed by a minor modification of Alg. 1 in Appendix C. In particular, one would omit lines 3 and 14-16, the amendment "by increasing constraints" in line 2, and the superscript "red". The set \mathcal{S}_1 contains all elements of $\mathcal{P}(\{1, \dots, q_{\mathcal{U}\mathcal{X}} + q_{\mathcal{T}}\})$ that are optimal active sets. An active set \mathcal{A} is op-

timal if the solution for the linear program (LP)

$$\min_{U, x(0), \lambda_{\mathcal{A}}, s_{\mathcal{I}}, t} -t \quad (6a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } F^T x(0) + HU + (G_{\mathcal{A}})^T \lambda_{\mathcal{A}} = 0, \quad (6b)$$

$$te_1 \leq \lambda_{\mathcal{A}}, \quad (6c)$$

$$G_{\mathcal{A}}U - E_{\mathcal{A}}x(0) - w_{\mathcal{A}} = 0, \quad (6d)$$

$$G_{\mathcal{I}}U - E_{\mathcal{I}}x(0) - w_{\mathcal{I}} + s_{\mathcal{I}} = 0, \quad (6e)$$

$$te_2 \leq s_{\mathcal{I}}, \quad t \geq 0, \quad (6f)$$

with $e_1 = (1, \dots, 1)^T \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{A}|}$, $e_2 = (1, \dots, 1)^T \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{I}|}$, Lagrangian multipliers $\lambda_{\mathcal{A}}$, and slack variables $s_{\mathcal{I}}$, exists [10, Sect. 3.1]. If it exists, we denote the solution to (6) with U^* , $x^*(0)$, $\lambda_{\mathcal{A}}^*$, $s_{\mathcal{I}}^*$, t^* . An additional criterion enables to efficiently identify active sets that are not optimal: We call active sets \mathcal{A} such that (6) without (6b) and (6c) has a solution (resp. has no solution) *feasible* (resp. *infeasible*). Feasibility is a necessary condition for optimality because the test for feasibility involves a subset of the constraints of the test for optimality. We collect all active sets that are detected as infeasible in $\mathcal{S}_1^{\text{pruned}}$. Any active set \mathcal{A} such that $\mathcal{A} \supseteq \tilde{\mathcal{A}}$ for an $\tilde{\mathcal{A}} \in \mathcal{S}_1^{\text{pruned}}$ is infeasible [10, Thm. 1] and thus not optimal. Discarding active sets because they are supersets of known infeasible active sets is further referred to as pruning. Pruning has the greatest impact when the active sets are tested in the order of increasing cardinality. For later use, the algorithm collects active sets such that the solution to (6) is $t^* = 0$ in $\mathcal{S}_1^{\text{degen}}$.

The solution \mathcal{S}_{N+1} for an increased horizon is calculated with the solution \mathcal{S}_N . Lemma 1 states a basic relation of the solutions for successive horizons, which is needed below.

Lemma 1 ([15, Cor. 3]) *Consider an OCP (1) with constraint order (5). Assume we know \mathcal{S}_N . Then*

$$\mathcal{S}_{N+1} = \mathcal{H}^{(1)} \cup \mathcal{H}^{(2)}, \quad (7)$$

with

$$\mathcal{H}^{(1)} = \{\mathcal{A} \in \mathcal{S}_N \mid \mathcal{A} \subseteq \{1, \dots, Nq_{\mathcal{U}\mathcal{X}}\}\}, \quad (8a)$$

$$\mathcal{H}^{(2)} \subseteq \left\{ \mathcal{A}_j \cup (\mathcal{A}_l \oplus \{q_{\mathcal{U}\mathcal{X}}\}) \mid \mathcal{A}_j \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Q}_0), \mathcal{A}_l \in \tilde{\mathcal{S}}_N \right\}, \quad (8b)$$

where the set $\tilde{\mathcal{S}}_N$ contains all elements of \mathcal{S}_N that have at least one active constraint in stage $k = N-1$ or $k = N$, i.e.,

$$\tilde{\mathcal{S}}_N = \{\mathcal{A} \in \mathcal{S}_N \mid \mathcal{A} \not\subseteq \{1, \dots, (N-1)q_{\mathcal{U}\mathcal{X}}\}\}. \quad (9)$$

The algorithm that implements Lem. 1 results from Alg. 2 in Appendix C if the superscript "red" is omitted.

All elements of \mathcal{S}_{N+1} are optimal active sets by definition. Therefore, only those elements of the superset in (8b) that are optimal active sets (i.e., their solution to (6) exists) are added to \mathcal{S}_{N+1} . The algorithm also implements pruning to identify active sets that are not optimal more efficiently. The set $\mathcal{S}_{N+1}^{\text{degen}}$ consists of those active sets $\mathcal{A} \in \mathcal{S}_N^{\text{degen}}$ that are elements of (8a) and those active sets in the superset in (8b) such that the solution to (6) is $t^* = 0$.

The algorithm for determining the solution \mathcal{M}_N for $N = N_{\max}$ results from Alg. 3 in Appendix C if line 11 is replaced by "add \mathcal{A}_k to \mathcal{M}_N ", and if the superscript "red" is omitted. The algorithm iteratively increases the horizon N and terminates either if $N = N_{\max}$ or if an N such that $\mathcal{S}_N = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{S}_N$ has been found with [15, Prop.1]. The set \mathcal{S}_N is reduced to \mathcal{M}_N by discarding those elements \mathcal{A} such that $G_{\mathcal{A}}$ does not have full row rank and those that define lower-dimensional polytopes. Only those elements \mathcal{A} that are elements of $\mathcal{S}_N^{\text{degen}}$, i.e., those that result $t^* = 0$ are tested for defining a full-dimensional polytope. The other elements are known to define a full-dimensional polytope according to [20, Thm. 2] because $t^* > 0$ implies strict inequality for both $G_{\mathcal{I}}U^* < w_{\mathcal{I}} + E_{\mathcal{I}}x^*(0)$ and $\lambda_{\mathcal{A}}^* > 0$.

3 Symmetries in active sets

In this section, we identify sets of symmetric active sets and identify properties that symmetric active sets have in common. We need Cor. 2 as a preparation. It establishes every constraint has a symmetric one for a pair $(\Theta, \Omega) \in \mathcal{G}$.

Corollary 2 Consider an OCP (1) and a pair (Θ, Ω) such that the OCP is symmetric to the pair with (3). Assume the OCP is reformulated as a QP (2). Then for every $i \in \mathcal{Q}$, there exists an $j \in \mathcal{Q}$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\{i\}} &= G_{\{j\}} (I^N \otimes \Omega), \\ E_{\{i\}} &= E_{\{j\}} \Theta, \\ w_{\{i\}} &= w_{\{j\}}. \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

The proof is stated in Appendix A.

Let $\pi^{(\Theta, \Omega)} : \mathcal{Q} \rightarrow \mathcal{Q}$ refer to the function with $j = \pi^{(\Theta, \Omega)}(i)$ from (10). The group properties of \mathcal{G} carry over to the functions $\pi^{(\Theta, \Omega)}$ for all $(\Theta, \Omega) \in \mathcal{G}$.

Lemma 3 Consider an OCP (1) and let \mathcal{G} contain all pairs (Θ, Ω) that satisfy (3). Then, the set of all $\pi^{(\Theta, \Omega)}$, $(\Theta, \Omega) \in \mathcal{G}$ is a permutation group on \mathcal{Q} .

The proof is stated in Appendix B.

Accordingly, we introduce the function $\Pi^{(\Theta, \Omega)} : \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Q}) \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Q})$, which maps all constraints in an active set $\mathcal{A} \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Q})$ for the pair (Θ, Ω) with $\pi^{(\Theta, \Omega)}$, by

$$\Pi^{(\Theta, \Omega)}(\mathcal{A}) := \{j \in \mathcal{Q} \mid j = \pi^{(\Theta, \Omega)}(i), i \in \mathcal{A}\}.$$

It follows from Lem. 3 that the set $\{\Pi^{(\Theta, \Omega)} \mid (\Theta, \Omega) \in \mathcal{G}\}$ is a permutation group on $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Q})$. We call the active set $\mathcal{A}_j = \Pi^{(\Theta, \Omega)}(\mathcal{A}_i)$ the symmetric active set to \mathcal{A}_i under the pair (Θ, Ω) .

The orbit $\mathcal{O}(\mathcal{A})$ of the active set \mathcal{A} refers to the set of symmetric active sets to \mathcal{A} under all pairs (Θ, Ω) that satisfy (3) for an arbitrary but fixed OCP (1)

$$\mathcal{O}(\mathcal{A}) := \left\{ \Pi^{(\Theta, \Omega)}(\mathcal{A}) \mid (\Theta, \Omega) \in \mathcal{G} \right\}. \quad (11)$$

The orbits of all active sets in $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Q})$ partition $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Q})$. We drop the argument \mathcal{A} in the notation of an orbit and simply denote it \mathcal{O} .

Corollaries 4 and 5 state properties that the elements of an orbit have in common.

Corollary 4 Consider an OCP (1). The active sets of an orbit are either all optimal or all not optimal.

PROOF. Consider two active sets \mathcal{A}_i and \mathcal{A}_j that are elements of the same orbit. It follows that there exists a pair $(\Theta, \Omega) \in \mathcal{G}$ such that $\mathcal{A}_j = \Pi^{(\Theta, \Omega)}(\mathcal{A}_i)$. Let the polytopes defined by \mathcal{A}_i and \mathcal{A}_j be denoted \mathcal{R}_i and \mathcal{R}_j , respectively. The pair (Θ, Ω) causes a state-space transformation of the optimal control law with Θ . Therefore,

$$\mathcal{R}_j = \Theta \circ \mathcal{R}_i, \quad (12)$$

according to the proof of Cor. 1 in [8]. This implies either both polytopes are not empty, i.e., both active sets are optimal, or both polytopes are empty, i.e., both active sets are not optimal. \square

Corollary 5 Consider an OCP (1). The polytopes defined by the active sets of an orbit are either all full-dimensional or all lower-dimensional in state-space.

PROOF. Consider two active sets \mathcal{A}_i and \mathcal{A}_j that are elements of the same orbit. It follows that there exists a pair $(\Theta, \Omega) \in \mathcal{G}$ such that $\mathcal{A}_j = \Pi^{(\Theta, \Omega)}(\mathcal{A}_i)$. Let the polytopes defined by \mathcal{A}_i and \mathcal{A}_j be denoted \mathcal{R}_i and \mathcal{R}_j , respectively. The claim can be proved by showing that, if \mathcal{R}_i is full-dimensional in state-space, then \mathcal{R}_j is full-dimensional in state-space. Assume \mathcal{R}_i is full-dimensional. Then there exist $n+1$ states $x_0, \dots, x_n \in \mathcal{R}_i$

such that the vectors $x_i - x_0$, $i = 1, \dots, n$ are linearly independent, i.e.,

$$x_n - x_0 = r_1(x_1 - x_0) + \dots + r_{n-1}(x_{n-1} - x_0) \quad (13)$$

with $r_1, \dots, r_{n-1} \in \mathbb{R}$ has no solution. It follows from (12) that $\Theta x_0, \dots, \Theta x_n \in \mathcal{R}_j$. The vectors $\Theta x_i - \Theta x_0$, $i = 1, \dots, n$ are linearly independent because

$$\begin{aligned} \Theta x_n - \Theta x_0 &= r_1(\Theta x_1 - \Theta x_0) + \\ &\dots + r_{n-1}(\Theta x_{n-1} - \Theta x_0), \end{aligned}$$

equals (13) if Θ^{-1} is multiplied from the left. The inverse Θ^{-1} exists by definition of the pair (Θ, Ω) in Sect. 2.1. It follows that \mathcal{R}_j is a full-dimensional state-space polytope. \square

3.1 Exploration strategy for the combinatorial tree

Combinatorial approaches calculate \mathcal{M}_N by identifying those elements of $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Q})$ that are optimal active sets and define full-dimensional polytopes for a QP (2). With Cors. 4 and 5, it is sufficient to test one active set and its polytope of each orbit for optimality and full-dimensionality, respectively, to get a result for all active sets in the orbit. This allows for a reduction in the computational effort of combinatorial approaches. We propose an exploration strategy for the active sets of $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Q})$ to efficiently identify those active sets that do not need to be tested.

Let a combinatorial tree (Fig. 1) represent all elements of $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Q})$. This rooted tree was first introduced in [18, Def. 2.2] as enumeration set tree and is used in many combinatorial approaches [10,9,1], where it is referred to as active set nodal tree, active set tree, and combinatorial search tree. Let the set $\mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A})$ contain all active sets in the subtree of \mathcal{A} , i.e., all descendants of \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{A} itself. Formally,

$$\mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A}) := \left\{ \mathcal{A} \cup \hat{\mathcal{A}} \mid \hat{\mathcal{A}} \in \mathcal{P}(\{\max(\mathcal{A}) + 1, \dots, q\}) \right\}. \quad (14)$$

Furthermore, active sets with identical cardinalities appear in the same level of the tree, and each level is ordered such that those active sets that contain the lowest constraint indices appear leftmost without restriction.

The elements of an orbit have identical cardinalities, see (11), and therefore appear on the same level of the combinatorial tree. Let the *primary* active set of an orbit \mathcal{O} be the element of the orbit that contains the lowest constraint indices, i.e.,

$$\mathcal{A} \in \mathcal{O} : \min(\mathcal{A} \setminus \hat{\mathcal{A}}) < \min(\hat{\mathcal{A}} \setminus \mathcal{A}) \forall \hat{\mathcal{A}} \in \mathcal{O} \setminus \mathcal{A}. \quad (15)$$

It follows that the primary active set is the element of the orbit that is located leftmost in the level of the combinatorial tree.

Assuming the elements of the combinatorial tree are explored in the order of increasing cardinality and from left to right in each level, then the primary element of each orbit is reached first. This implies the non-primary elements need not be tested. The following Lemma can be used to efficiently identify active sets that are non-primary.

Lemma 6 Consider an OCP (1) and all pairs (Θ, Ω) that satisfy (3). If \mathcal{A} is an active set that is non-primary, then all elements of $\mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A})$ are non-primary.

PROOF. Consider an active set \mathcal{A}_i that is non-primary. Let the primary active set in its orbit be \mathcal{A}_p . This implies there exists a pair $(\Theta_p, \Omega_p) \in \mathcal{G}$ such that $\Pi^{(\Theta_p, \Omega_p)}(\mathcal{A}_i) = \mathcal{A}_p$. Furthermore, by definition of the primary active set (15)

$$\min(\mathcal{A}_p \setminus \mathcal{A}_i) < \min(\mathcal{A}_i \setminus \mathcal{A}_p). \quad (16)$$

Consider an arbitrary active set $\mathcal{A}_j \in \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A}_i)$. It follows from (14) that there exists an $\hat{\mathcal{A}}_i$ such that

$$\mathcal{A}_j = \mathcal{A}_i \cup \hat{\mathcal{A}}_i, \hat{\mathcal{A}}_i \in \mathcal{P}(\{\max(\mathcal{A}_i) + 1, \dots, q\}). \quad (17)$$

Now let $\Pi^{(\Theta_p, \Omega_p)}(\mathcal{A}_j) = \mathcal{A}_k$. Then, \mathcal{A}_k and \mathcal{A}_j are elements of the same orbit. $\mathcal{A}_j \supseteq \mathcal{A}_i$ according to (17) implies $\Pi^{(\Theta_p, \Omega_p)}(\mathcal{A}_j) \supseteq \Pi^{(\Theta_p, \Omega_p)}(\mathcal{A}_i)$ and therefore,

$$\mathcal{A}_k \supseteq \mathcal{A}_p. \quad (18)$$

It remains to show that \mathcal{A}_k contains lower indices than \mathcal{A}_j , i.e.,

$$\min(\mathcal{A}_k \setminus \mathcal{A}_j) < \min(\mathcal{A}_j \setminus \mathcal{A}_k), \quad (19)$$

and hence, \mathcal{A}_j is a non-primary active set. Inserting (17) and (18) in (19) gives

$$\begin{aligned} \min((\mathcal{A}_p \cup \hat{\mathcal{A}}_p) \setminus (\mathcal{A}_i \cup \hat{\mathcal{A}}_i)) \\ < \min((\mathcal{A}_i \cup \hat{\mathcal{A}}_i) \setminus (\mathcal{A}_p \cup \hat{\mathcal{A}}_p)), \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

with $\hat{\mathcal{A}}_i \in \mathcal{P}(\{\max(\mathcal{A}_i) + 1, \dots, q\})$ and $\hat{\mathcal{A}}_p \in \mathcal{P}(\{1, \dots, q\})$. Since $\mathcal{A}_i \neq \mathcal{A}_p$, (20) is equivalent to

$$\min((\mathcal{A}_p \cup \hat{\mathcal{A}}_p) \setminus \mathcal{A}_i) < \min(\mathcal{A}_i \setminus (\mathcal{A}_p \cup \hat{\mathcal{A}}_p)). \quad (21)$$

The expression in (21) is true for any $\hat{\mathcal{A}}_p$ because (16) holds. \square

Example 7 We illustrate Lem. 6 for an artificial symmetric problem with four constraints. The combinatorial tree shown in Fig. 1 contains all elements of $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Q})$, $\mathcal{Q} = \{1, \dots, 4\}$. Assume there are four symmetries $(\Theta_i, \Omega_i) \in$

Fig. 1. Combinatorial tree for Example 7. Primary active sets are shown in black, active sets that are non-primary are shown in grey.

\mathcal{G} , $i = 1, \dots, 4$ such that the functions $\pi^{(\Theta_i, \Omega_i)}$, $i = 1, \dots, 4$ are in two-line notation

$$\begin{aligned} \pi^{(\Theta_1, \Omega_1)} &= \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \end{pmatrix}, & \pi^{(\Theta_2, \Omega_2)} &= \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 2 & 3 & 4 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \\ \pi^{(\Theta_3, \Omega_3)} &= \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 3 & 4 & 1 & 2 \end{pmatrix}, & \pi^{(\Theta_4, \Omega_4)} &= \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 4 & 1 & 2 & 3 \end{pmatrix}, \end{aligned}$$

where the first row lists all elements of \mathcal{Q} , and for each of those elements, the second row lists the image under the permutation $\pi^{(\Theta_i, \Omega_i)}$. We develop the orbit for the active set $\{1, 2\}$ as an example. The orbit contains the active sets $\Pi^{(\Theta_i, \Omega_i)}(\{1, 2\})$ for $i = 1, \dots, 4$, where $\Pi^{(\Theta_i, \Omega_i)}$ maps all elements of $\{1, 2\}$ with $\pi^{(\Theta_i, \Omega_i)}$. It results

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi^{(\Theta_1, \Omega_1)}(\{1, 2\}) &= \{1, 2\}, & \Pi^{(\Theta_2, \Omega_2)}(\{1, 2\}) &= \{2, 3\}, \\ \Pi^{(\Theta_3, \Omega_3)}(\{1, 2\}) &= \{3, 4\}, & \Pi^{(\Theta_4, \Omega_4)}(\{1, 2\}) &= \{1, 4\}, \end{aligned}$$

and therefore,

$$\mathcal{O}_1 = \{\{\mathbf{1, 2}\}, \{2, 3\}, \{3, 4\}, \{1, 4\}\}.$$

The orbits for the remaining active sets in $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Q})$ are

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{O}_2 &= \{\{\}\}, & \mathcal{O}_3 &= \{\{\mathbf{1}\}, \{2\}, \{3\}, \{4\}\}, \\ \mathcal{O}_4 &= \{\{\mathbf{1, 3}\}, \{2, 4\}\}, \\ \mathcal{O}_5 &= \{\{\mathbf{1, 2, 3}\}, \{2, 3, 4\}, \{1, 3, 4\}, \{1, 2, 4\}\}, \\ \mathcal{O}_6 &= \{\{\mathbf{1, 2, 3, 4}\}\}. \end{aligned}$$

The set of all orbits partitions $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Q})$. We marked the primary active set of each orbit in bold letters. It can be seen in Fig. 1 that the subtrees of non-primary active sets only contain non-primary active sets as is stated in Lem. 6.

4 Dynamic programming approach for symmetric OCP

In this section, we use the results from Sect. 3 to improve the DP approach from [15]. All algorithms referred to in this chapter are stated in Appendix C. The improvement of the algorithm is achieved by only calculating the primary active sets in the solution and then constructing the entire solution on this basis at the end. Let $\mathcal{S}_N^{\text{red}}$ denote the reduced solution set containing all $\mathcal{A} \in \mathcal{S}_N$ that are primary active sets.

The algorithm for determining the reduced solution $\mathcal{S}_1^{\text{red}}$ for the initial horizon is stated in Alg. 1. The set $\mathcal{S}_1^{\text{red}}$ consists of those elements of $\mathcal{P}(\{1, \dots, qux + q\tau\})$ that are primary and optimal. The algorithm collects non-primary active sets in the set $\mathcal{S}_1^{\text{nonprim}}$ which is initialized as empty (line 1). Any active set \mathcal{A} such that $\mathcal{A} \in \mathcal{D}(\bar{\mathcal{A}})$ for an $\bar{\mathcal{A}} \in \mathcal{S}_1^{\text{nonprim}}$ is non-primary with Lem. 6 and thus discarded (line 3). All active sets in $\mathcal{P}(\{1, \dots, qux + q\tau\})$ are processed in the order of increasing cardinality and increasing constraint indices (line 2). When transferred to a combinatorial tree as in Fig. 1, this strategy proceeds from top to bottom, and in each level from left to right. This way, pruning has the most impact and the primary active sets of each orbit are processed first. The elements of the orbit of a primary active set, except the primary active set itself, are non-primary by definition and added to $\mathcal{S}_1^{\text{nonprim}}$ if not already elements of a set $\mathcal{D}(\bar{\mathcal{A}})$, $\bar{\mathcal{A}} \in \mathcal{S}_1^{\text{nonprim}}$ (lines 14-16). The remaining lines in the algorithm (lines 4-13) are unchanged from the DP approach.

Corollary 8 is used in Alg. 2 to construct the reduced solution $\mathcal{S}_{N+1}^{\text{red}}$ for an increased horizon from the reduced solution $\mathcal{S}_N^{\text{red}}$ for the current horizon. It results from modifying [14, Cor. 5] to the general symmetries considered in this paper.

Corollary 8 Consider an OCP (1) with constraint order (5). Assume we know $\mathcal{S}_N^{\text{red}}$. Then

$$\mathcal{S}_{N+1}^{\text{red}} = \mathcal{H}^{(1), \text{red}} \cup \mathcal{H}^{(2), \text{red}},$$

with

$$\mathcal{H}^{(1), \text{red}} = \{\mathcal{A} \in \mathcal{S}_N^{\text{red}} \mid \mathcal{A} \subseteq \{1, \dots, Nqux\}\}, \quad (22a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{H}^{(2), \text{red}} &\subseteq \left\{ \mathcal{A}_j \cup (\mathcal{A}_l \oplus \{qux\}) \mid \right. \\ &\quad \left. \mathcal{A}_j \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Q}_0), \mathcal{A}_l \in \tilde{\mathcal{S}}_N^{\text{red}} \right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (22b)$$

where $\tilde{\mathcal{S}}_N^{\text{red}}$ contains all elements of $\mathcal{S}_N^{\text{red}}$ that have at least one active constraint in stage $k = N - 1$ or $k = N$, i.e.,

$$\tilde{\mathcal{S}}_N^{\text{red}} = \{\mathcal{A} \in \mathcal{S}_N^{\text{red}} \mid \mathcal{A} \not\subseteq \{1, \dots, (N-1)qux\}\}.$$

PROOF. According to (7) $\mathcal{S}_{N+1} = \mathcal{H}^{(1)} \cup \mathcal{H}^{(2)}$, where $\mathcal{H}^{(1)}$ and $\mathcal{H}^{(2)}$ are defined in (8a) and (8b), respectively. The reduced solution $\mathcal{S}_{N+1}^{\text{red}}$ contains all primary active sets of \mathcal{S}_{N+1} . Let $\mathcal{F}^{(1)}$ and $\mathcal{F}^{(2)}$ contain all primary active sets of $\mathcal{H}^{(1)}$ and $\mathcal{H}^{(2)}$, respectively. It follows that $\mathcal{S}_{N+1}^{\text{red}} = \mathcal{F}^{(1)} \cup \mathcal{F}^{(2)}$. We show that $\mathcal{F}^{(1)} = \mathcal{H}^{(1),\text{red}}$ and $\mathcal{F}^{(1)} = \mathcal{H}^{(2),\text{red}}$. $\mathcal{F}^{(1)}$ is the subset of all primary active sets of

$$\mathcal{H}^{(1)} = \{\mathcal{A} | \mathcal{A} \subseteq \{1, \dots, Nq_{\mathcal{U}\mathcal{X}}\}, \mathcal{A} \in \mathcal{S}_N\}.$$

Non-primary active sets can be removed from $\mathcal{H}^{(1)}$ by replacing \mathcal{S}_N by $\mathcal{S}_N^{\text{red}}$,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}^{(1)} &= \{\mathcal{A} | \mathcal{A} \subseteq \{1, \dots, Nq_{\mathcal{U}\mathcal{X}}\}, \mathcal{A} \in \mathcal{S}_N^{\text{red}}\} \\ &= \mathcal{H}^{(1),\text{red}}. \end{aligned}$$

In the same way, the set $\mathcal{F}^{(2)}$ results from replacing \mathcal{S}_N by $\mathcal{S}_N^{\text{red}}$ in

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{H}^{(2)} &\subseteq \{\mathcal{A} | \mathcal{A} = \mathcal{A}_j \cup (\mathcal{A}_l \oplus \{q_{\mathcal{U}\mathcal{X}}\}), \mathcal{A}_j \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Q}_0), \\ &\quad \mathcal{A}_l \not\subseteq \{1, \dots, (N-1)q_{\mathcal{U}\mathcal{X}}\}, \mathcal{A}_l \in \mathcal{S}_N\}, \end{aligned}$$

which yields

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}^{(2)} &\subseteq \{\mathcal{A} | \mathcal{A} = \mathcal{A}_j \cup (\mathcal{A}_l \oplus \{q_{\mathcal{U}\mathcal{X}}\}), \mathcal{A}_j \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Q}_0), \\ &\quad \mathcal{A}_l \not\subseteq \{1, \dots, (N-1)q_{\mathcal{U}\mathcal{X}}\}, \mathcal{A}_l \in \mathcal{S}_N^{\text{red}}\}. \end{aligned}$$

With $\tilde{\mathcal{S}}_N^{\text{red}} = \{\mathcal{A} \in \mathcal{S}_N^{\text{red}} | \mathcal{A} \not\subseteq \{1, \dots, (N-1)q_{\mathcal{U}\mathcal{X}}\}\}$ this results in

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}^{(2)} &\subseteq \{\mathcal{A} | \mathcal{A} = \mathcal{A}_j \cup (\mathcal{A}_l \oplus \{q_{\mathcal{U}\mathcal{X}}\}), \mathcal{A}_j \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Q}_0), \\ &\quad \mathcal{A}_l \in \tilde{\mathcal{S}}_N^{\text{red}}\}, \end{aligned}$$

and hence, $\mathcal{F}^{(2)} = \mathcal{H}^{(2),\text{red}}$. \square

The relation of the reduced solutions for horizon N to those for horizon $N+1$ in Cor. 8 is similar to the corresponding relation in Lem. 1. Therefore, the procedure for determining the reduced solution for the increased horizon in Alg. 2 is similar to the DP approach, but requires, as inputs and outputs, the reduced solutions $\mathcal{S}_N^{\text{red}}$ and $\mathcal{S}_{N+1}^{\text{red}}$, respectively, instead of the solutions \mathcal{S}_N and \mathcal{S}_{N+1} .

The overall algorithm is stated in Alg. 3. It proceeds analogously to the DP approach, but adds the whole orbit to \mathcal{M}_N whenever an active set is detected to be part of \mathcal{M}_N (lines 12, 14). This is because if an active set is optimal and defines a full-dimensional polytope, the same holds for the elements of its orbit (Cors. 4 and 5).

5 Example

We illustrate how the approach introduced in Sect. 4 determines the solution with an example.

Example 9 Consider the system [6, Example 1]

$$x(k+1) = \begin{pmatrix} 2 & 1 \\ -1 & 2 \end{pmatrix} x(k) + \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} u(k),$$

with input and state constraints $|u_{1,2}(k)| \leq 1$ and $|x_{1,2}(k)| \leq 1$, respectively, and cost function matrices $Q = I^2$, $R = 5000 \cdot I^2$. The terminal cost P and terminal set \mathcal{T} are as described in Sect. 2.

This example has four pairs $(\Theta_i, \Omega_i) \in \mathcal{G}$, $i = 1, \dots, 4$, that satisfy (3),

$$\begin{aligned} (\Theta_1, \Omega_1) &= (I^2, I^2), (\Theta_2, \Omega_2) = \left(\begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \right), \\ (\Theta_3, \Omega_3) &= (-I^2, -I^2), (\Theta_4, \Omega_4) = (\Theta_2^{-1}, \Omega_2^{-1}) \end{aligned}$$

An approach to identifying the pairs is given in [7].

We illustrate the construction of the solution for Example 9 with Fig. 2. Figure 2a shows the reduced solution for the initial horizon $N = 1$ calculated with Alg. 1. The reduced solution for the increased horizon $N = 2$ in Fig. 2b is determined based on the reduced solution for $N = 1$ with Alg. 2. Repeatedly applying Alg. 2 provides the reduced solution for the target horizon, which is $N_{\text{max}} = 5$ in this example (Fig. 2c). Figure 2d shows the solution for the target horizon. It results by adding all elements of the orbits of the active sets in the reduced solution with Alg. 3.

5.1 Computational effort

We analyze the reduction of the computational effort that is achieved by exploiting symmetries. Figure 3 illustrates the numbers of executed optimality tests with (6) and feasibility tests with (6) without (6b) and (6c) carried out for the DP approach presented in [15] and the improved DP approach presented in this paper for different horizons. The computational effort required for solving an LP is relatively high, therefore these numbers suit as indicators for the computational effort. Independently of the horizon, the numbers of optimality and feasibility tests for the approach presented in this paper are almost 75% lower, which implies its computational effort is almost decreased by a factor of four.

The reduction results for the following reasons. The set of explored active sets for the initial horizon $N = 1$ is $\mathcal{P}(\{1, \dots, q_{\mathcal{U}\mathcal{X}} + q_{\mathcal{T}}\})$ (line 2 in Alg. 1). Both approaches

Fig. 2. State-space partition for Example 9. Gray polytopes are defined by active sets that are elements of the reduced solution. White polytopes are defined by the active sets in the solution that are not elements of the reduced solution in Fig. 2d.

Fig. 3. Numbers of executed tests for the approach presented in [15] (circles) and for Alg. 3 (crosses) for Example 9 as a function of the horizon.

execute optimality tests only for a subset of these active sets. The DP approach discards those that are supersets of known infeasible active sets, the approach presented in this paper additionally discards those that are non-primary (line 3 in Alg. 1). It follows that the algorithm presented in this paper executes fewer optimality tests. Feasibility tests are executed for all active sets that were tested for optimality and were identified as not optimal. Thus, fewer optimality tests entail fewer feasibility tests. For any increased horizon $N + 1$, the number of explored active sets for the DP approach depends on the cardinality of the solution \mathcal{S}_N , and for the approach presented in this paper it depends on the cardinality of the reduced solution $\mathcal{S}_N^{\text{red}}$ (line 3 in Alg. 2) **which includes only the primary active sets of \mathcal{S}_N** . Thus, there result fewer ex-

plored active sets for the approach presented in this paper, and consequently, fewer optimality and feasibility tests are executed.

It follows that the smaller the relation between primary and non-primary active sets, the higher the reduction of the computational effort. A small relation results, if the average number of elements of the orbits is high, i.e., if the problem has many symmetries. More precisely, if a problem has g symmetries, then each orbit contains up to g elements, see (11), and the computational effort of the approach presented in this paper can decrease down to $\frac{1}{g}$ of the computational effort of the DP approach.

6 Conclusion

In this work, it was shown that symmetries in constrained linear-quadratic OCPs entail sets of active sets that are symmetric to each other, so-called orbits. The elements of an orbit have properties in common. Based on this, a strategy for improving combinatorial approaches for constrained linear-quadratic OCPs with symmetries was proposed. The computational effort for the improved approach is almost reduced to $\frac{1}{g}$ of the computational effort for the approach that does not consider symmetries, where g denotes the number of symmetries of the OCP. We stress this is an improvement over algorithms that already are considerably faster than a naïve enumeration.

The results of this paper can be also used to implement the orbit controller introduced in [8, Sect. 5] with less computational effort: A by-product of the approach proposed in this paper is the reduced solution which contains only one active set out of each orbit. The reduced solution makes the synthesis in [8, Sect. 5B] superfluous. This topic will be investigated in future.

A Proof of Cor. 2

PROOF. \mathcal{X} , \mathcal{U} and \mathcal{T} can be defined by intersections of a finite number of halfspaces. Since \mathcal{X} , \mathcal{U} and \mathcal{T} are symmetric to the pair (Θ, Ω) by assumption, the conditions (3b) hold. As a consequence, there exist $T^{\mathcal{U}}$, $T^{\mathcal{X}}$, $T^{\mathcal{T}}$, and $d^{\mathcal{U}}$, $d^{\mathcal{X}}$, $d^{\mathcal{T}}$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{U} &= \left\{ u \in \mathbb{R}^m \mid \begin{pmatrix} T^{\mathcal{U}} \\ T^{\mathcal{U}\Omega} \end{pmatrix} u \leq \begin{pmatrix} d^{\mathcal{U}} \\ d^{\mathcal{U}} \end{pmatrix} \right\}, \\ \mathcal{X} &= \left\{ x \in \mathbb{R}^n \mid \begin{pmatrix} T^{\mathcal{X}} \\ T^{\mathcal{X}\Theta} \end{pmatrix} x \leq \begin{pmatrix} d^{\mathcal{X}} \\ d^{\mathcal{X}} \end{pmatrix} \right\}, \\ \mathcal{T} &= \left\{ x \in \mathbb{R}^n \mid \begin{pmatrix} T^{\mathcal{T}} \\ T^{\mathcal{T}\Theta} \end{pmatrix} x \leq \begin{pmatrix} d^{\mathcal{T}} \\ d^{\mathcal{T}} \end{pmatrix} \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

We now investigate how the expressions in (A.1) relate to the input, state, and terminal constraints in the OCP (1). The input constraints (1c) expressed with (A.1) yield

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0^{m \times km} & T^{\mathcal{U}} & 0^{m \times (N-k-1)m} \\ 0^{m \times km} & T^{\mathcal{U}} \Omega & 0^{m \times (N-k-1)m} \end{pmatrix} U \leq \begin{pmatrix} d^{\mathcal{U}} \\ d^{\mathcal{U}} \end{pmatrix},$$

$$k = 0, \dots, N-1.$$

This can be reformulated to

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0^{m \times km} & T^{\mathcal{U}} & 0^{m \times (N-k-1)m} \\ 0^{m \times km} & T^{\mathcal{U}} \Omega & 0^{m \times (N-k-1)m} \end{pmatrix} \cdot (I^N \otimes \Omega) \begin{pmatrix} U \\ U \end{pmatrix} \leq \begin{pmatrix} d^{\mathcal{U}} \\ d^{\mathcal{U}} \end{pmatrix}, \quad k = 0, \dots, N-1. \quad (\text{A.2})$$

As preparation for dealing with the state and terminal constraints, we express a state $x(k)$, $k > 0$ with $x(0)$ and the input variables U with (1b),

$$x(k) = \begin{pmatrix} A^{k-1} B & A^{k-2} B & \dots & B & 0^{n \times (N-k)n} \end{pmatrix} U + A^k x(0).$$

The state constraints (1d) expressed with (A.1) then yield

$$\begin{pmatrix} T^{\mathcal{X}} \\ T^{\mathcal{X}} \Theta \end{pmatrix} x(0) \leq \begin{pmatrix} d^{\mathcal{X}} \\ d^{\mathcal{X}} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (\text{A.3a})$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} T^{\mathcal{X}} \begin{pmatrix} A^{k-1} B & A^{k-2} B & \dots & B & 0^{n \times (N-k)n} \end{pmatrix} \\ T^{\mathcal{X}} \Theta \begin{pmatrix} A^{k-1} B & A^{k-2} B & \dots & B & 0^{n \times (N-k)n} \end{pmatrix} \end{pmatrix} U + \begin{pmatrix} T^{\mathcal{X}} A^k \\ T^{\mathcal{X}} \Theta A^k \end{pmatrix} x(0) \leq \begin{pmatrix} d^{\mathcal{X}} \\ d^{\mathcal{X}} \end{pmatrix}, \quad k = 1, \dots, N-1. \quad (\text{A.3b})$$

The second inequality (A.3b) results with (3a)

$$\begin{pmatrix} T^{\mathcal{X}} \begin{pmatrix} A^{k-1} B & A^{k-2} B & \dots & B & 0^{n \times (N-k)n} \end{pmatrix} \\ T^{\mathcal{X}} \begin{pmatrix} A^{k-1} B & A^{k-2} B & \dots & B & 0^{n \times (N-k)n} \end{pmatrix} \cdot (I^N \otimes \Omega) \end{pmatrix} \cdot U + \begin{pmatrix} T^{\mathcal{X}} A^k \\ T^{\mathcal{X}} A^k \Theta \end{pmatrix} x(0) \leq \begin{pmatrix} d^{\mathcal{X}} \\ d^{\mathcal{X}} \end{pmatrix}, \quad k = 1, \dots, N-1. \quad (\text{A.4})$$

The constraints on the terminal stage (1e) expressed with (A.1) yield

$$\begin{pmatrix} T^{\mathcal{T}} \begin{pmatrix} A^{N-1} B & \dots & B \end{pmatrix} \\ T^{\mathcal{T}} \Theta \begin{pmatrix} A^{N-1} B & \dots & B \end{pmatrix} \end{pmatrix} U + \begin{pmatrix} T^{\mathcal{T}} A^N \\ T^{\mathcal{T}} \Theta A^N \end{pmatrix} x(0) \leq \begin{pmatrix} d^{\mathcal{T}} \\ d^{\mathcal{T}} \end{pmatrix}.$$

This results with (3a)

$$\begin{pmatrix} T^{\mathcal{T}} \begin{pmatrix} A^{N-1} B & \dots & B \end{pmatrix} \\ T^{\mathcal{T}} \begin{pmatrix} A^{N-1} B & \dots & B \end{pmatrix} \cdot (I^N \otimes \Omega) \end{pmatrix} U + \begin{pmatrix} T^{\mathcal{T}} A^N \\ T^{\mathcal{T}} A^N \Theta \end{pmatrix} x(0) \leq \begin{pmatrix} d^{\mathcal{T}} \\ d^{\mathcal{T}} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (\text{A.5})$$

The form $GU \leq Ex(0) + w$ can be obtained by moving all terms that depend on $x(0)$ to the right-hand side in (A.2), (A.3a), (A.4), and (A.5). $GU \leq Ex(0) + w$ inherits the alternating rows of (A.2), (A.3a), (A.4), and (A.5), so for every constraint i there is a constraint j such that $G_{\{i\}} = G_{\{j\}} (I^N \otimes \Omega)$, $E_{\{i\}} = E_{\{j\}} \Theta$ and $w_{\{i\}} = w_{\{j\}}$. \square

B Proof of Lem. 3

PROOF. We show that the set of all $\pi^{(\Theta, \Omega)}$, $(\Theta, \Omega) \in \mathcal{G}$ satisfies the group axioms.

Associativity: The composition of functions is associative, see, e.g., [13, p. 28].

Identity: Consider the pair (I^n, I^m) and a constraint $i \in \mathcal{Q}$. For $j = \pi^{(I^n, I^m)}(i)$ the conditions in (10) are

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\{i\}} = G_{\{j\}} (I^N \otimes I^m) &\Leftrightarrow G_{\{i\}} = G_{\{j\}}, \\ E_{\{i\}} = E_{\{j\}} I^n &\Leftrightarrow E_{\{i\}} = E_{\{j\}}, \\ w_{\{i\}} = w_{\{j\}} & \end{aligned}$$

This implies $\pi^{(I^n, I^m)}(i) = i$. With (4a) this implies $(I^n, I^m) \in \mathcal{G}$.

Invertibility: Consider a pair $(\Theta, \Omega) \in \mathcal{G}$ and a constraint $i \in \mathcal{Q}$. For $j = \pi^{(\Theta, \Omega)}(i)$ the conditions in (10) are

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\{j\}} = G_{\{i\}} (I^N \otimes \Omega^{-1}), \\ E_{\{j\}} = E_{\{i\}} \Theta^{-1}, \\ w_{\{j\}} = w_{\{i\}}. \end{aligned}$$

This implies $i = \pi^{(\Theta^{-1}, \Omega^{-1})}(j)$. With (4b) this implies $(\Theta^{-1}, \Omega^{-1}) \in \mathcal{G}$.

Closure: Consider two pairs $(\Theta_1, \Omega_1), (\Theta_2, \Omega_2) \in \mathcal{G}$ and a constraint $i \in \mathcal{Q}$. For the function composition $j = \pi^{(\Theta_2, \Omega_2)}(\pi^{(\Theta_1, \Omega_1)}(i))$ the conditions in (10) are

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\{i\}} &= (G_{\{j\}}(I^N \otimes \Omega_1))(I^N \otimes \Omega_2) \\ &\Leftrightarrow G_{\{i\}} = G_{\{j\}}(I^N \otimes (\Omega_1 \Omega_2)), \\ E_{\{i\}} &= (E_{\{j\}} \Theta_1) \Theta_2 \Leftrightarrow E_{\{i\}} = E_{\{j\}}(\Theta_1 \Theta_2), \\ w_{\{i\}} &= w_{\{j\}} \Leftrightarrow w_{\{i\}} = w_{\{j\}}. \end{aligned}$$

This implies $j = \pi^{(\Theta_1 \Theta_2, \Omega_1 \Omega_2)}(i)$. With (4c) this implies $(\Theta_1 \Theta_2, \Omega_1 \Omega_2) \in \mathcal{G}$. \square

C Algorithms from Sect. 4

Algorithm 1: Determination of $\mathcal{S}_1^{\text{red}}$

```

1 Initialization: set  $\mathcal{S}_1^{\text{red}} = \emptyset, \mathcal{S}_1^{\text{degen}} = \emptyset,$ 
 $\mathcal{S}_1^{\text{pruned}} = \emptyset$  and  $\mathcal{S}_1^{\text{nonprim}} = \emptyset$ 
2 for every  $\mathcal{A}_i \in \mathcal{P}(\{1, \dots, qux + q_T\})$  by incr.
   cardinality and by increasing constraints do
3   if  $\mathcal{A}_i \notin \mathcal{D}(\bar{\mathcal{A}})$  for all  $\bar{\mathcal{A}} \in \mathcal{S}_1^{\text{nonprim}}$  then
4     if  $\mathcal{A}_i \not\supseteq \bar{\mathcal{A}}$  for all  $\bar{\mathcal{A}} \in \mathcal{S}_1^{\text{pruned}}$  then
5       solve (6) for QP with horizon 1
6       if solution exists then
7         add  $\mathcal{A}_i$  to  $\mathcal{S}_1^{\text{red}}$ 
8         if solution  $t^* = 0$  then
9           add  $\mathcal{A}_i$  to  $\mathcal{S}_1^{\text{degen}}$ 
10      else
11        solve (6) without (6b) and (6c) for
          QP with horizon 1
12        if no solution exists then
13          add  $\mathcal{A}_i$  to  $\mathcal{S}_1^{\text{pruned}}$ 
14      for every  $\mathcal{A}_j \in \mathcal{O}(\mathcal{A}_i) \setminus \mathcal{A}_i$  do
15        if  $\mathcal{A}_j \notin \mathcal{D}(\bar{\mathcal{A}})$  for all  $\bar{\mathcal{A}} \in \mathcal{S}_1^{\text{nonprim}}$  then
16          add  $\mathcal{A}_j$  to  $\mathcal{S}_1^{\text{nonprim}}$ 
17 Output:  $\mathcal{S}_1^{\text{red}}, \mathcal{S}_1^{\text{degen}}$ 

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References

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Algorithm 2: Determination of $\mathcal{S}_{N+1}^{\text{red}}$ from $\mathcal{S}_N^{\text{red}}$

```

1 Input:  $\mathcal{S}_N^{\text{red}}, \mathcal{S}_N^{\text{degen}}$ 
2 Initialization: set  $\mathcal{S}_{N+1}^{\text{red}} = \emptyset, \mathcal{S}_{N+1}^{\text{degen}}$  and
 $\mathcal{S}_{N+1}^{\text{pruned}} = \emptyset$ 
3 for every  $\mathcal{A}_l \in \mathcal{S}_N^{\text{red}}$  do
4   if  $\mathcal{A}_l \subseteq \{1, \dots, Nqux\}$  then
5     add  $\mathcal{A}_l$  to  $\mathcal{S}_{N+1}^{\text{red}}$ 
6     if  $\mathcal{A}_l \in \mathcal{S}_N^{\text{degen}}$  then
7       add  $\mathcal{A}_l$  to  $\mathcal{S}_{N+1}^{\text{degen}}$ 
8   if  $\mathcal{A}_l \not\subseteq \{1, \dots, (N-1)qux\}$  then
9     for every  $\mathcal{A}_i = \mathcal{A}_j \cup (\mathcal{A}_l \oplus \{qux\})$  with
        $\mathcal{A}_j \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Q}_0)$  by increasing cardinality do
10      if  $\mathcal{A}_i \not\supseteq \bar{\mathcal{A}}$  for all  $\bar{\mathcal{A}} \in \mathcal{S}_{N+1}^{\text{pruned}}$  then
11        solve (6) for QP for horizon  $N+1$ 
12        if solution exists then
13          add  $\mathcal{A}_i$  to  $\mathcal{S}_{N+1}^{\text{red}}$ 
14          if solution  $t^* = 0$  then
15            add  $\mathcal{A}_i$  to  $\mathcal{S}_{N+1}^{\text{degen}}$ 
16        else
17          solve (6) without (6b) and (6c)
           for QP for horizon  $N+1$ 
18          if no solution exists then
19            add  $\mathcal{A}_i$  to  $\mathcal{S}_{N+1}^{\text{pruned}}$ 
20 Output:  $\mathcal{S}_{N+1}^{\text{red}}, \mathcal{S}_{N+1}^{\text{degen}}$ 

```

Algorithm 3: Dynamic programming approach to solving symmetric constrained linear-quadratic OCPs

```

1 Input:  $\mathcal{S}_1^{\text{red}}, \mathcal{S}_1^{\text{degen}}$  (from Alg. 1),  $N_{\max} \geq 1$ 
2 Initialization: set  $\mathcal{M}_N = \emptyset$ 
3 for  $N = 1$  to  $N_{\max} - 1$  do
4   determine  $\mathcal{S}_{N+1}^{\text{red}}$  and  $\mathcal{S}_{N+1}^{\text{degen}}$  with Alg. 2
5   if  $\mathcal{S}_{N+1}^{\text{red}} \subseteq \mathcal{P}(\{1, \dots, Nqux\})$  then
6     break
7    $N = N + 1$ 
8 for every  $\mathcal{A}_k \in \mathcal{S}_N^{\text{red}}$  do
9   if  $\text{rowrank}(G_{\mathcal{A}_k}) = |\mathcal{A}_k|$  then
10    if  $\mathcal{A}_k \notin \mathcal{S}_N^{\text{degen}}$  or polytope def. by  $\mathcal{A}_k$ 
       full-dimensional then
11      add all elements of  $\mathcal{O}(\mathcal{A}_k)$  to  $\mathcal{M}_N$ 
12 Output:  $\mathcal{M}_N$ 

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